

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

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D2.4 – FIRST REPORT ON INTERCONNECTION OF THIRD PARTIES, CI/CD AND POLICIES

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Abstract	This deliverable reports the planning for the third parties' integration together with the different activities that have already been done to allow it and the documentation created for helping in the process.
Keywords	Integration methodology, planning, information gathering, integration process, issue solving

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

According to the project's objectives, the COVID-X sandbox is defined as a complete environment for integration and management of public and private health data sources where a common distributed data lake is provided for the selected third parties to run and validate their own tools and solutions. Based on this idea, a specific plan should be designed for helping these actors in the integration process, covering different aspects such as data accessing, security and follow up. For this reason, this document presents the methodology for allowing third parties to be integrated within the COVID-X sandbox. This document also describes the documentation generated through the integration process for helping the third parties to complete it. It also provides a complete description of the integration process, providing details about how the different objectives have been achieved, particularly for these tasks:

- RBAC provision
- Data ingestion
- Local deployment
- Software integration

Finally, this document defines the issue solving process followed during the integration process, describing how the Consortium has guided and helped the different solutions in completing the process and finally accessing and using the sandbox for their own purposes.

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ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-X	Innovation action supported by the European Commission in the framework of the EC call SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
RBAC	Role based access control
VCS	Version Control System

1 General methodology definition

With the aim of accelerating the testing and validation of different solutions against the Covid-19, this project promotes a complete environment for data-driven tools deployment based on a multi-layer sandbox. This environment enables, among others, different methods for resource sharing and reuse according to different main open issues that we call project challenges.

The Covid-X challenges have been clinically defined and represent current fields of interests for external organizations which may provide valuable solutions for this health crisis by applying for the different open calls. Once selected, these third parties are not only allowed to use real clinical datasets, but also to perform other activities such as additional data integration and real-environment code execution for evaluating their solutions among real data.

The correct integration of these third parties in the platform is vital for the optimal execution of the project, and several elements and options need to be considered. For this reason, a complete methodology has been defined, composed by five specific steps as can be seen in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. GENERAL INTEGRATION METHODOLOGY FOR THIRD-PARTIES IN THE COVID-X PROJECT

Regardless of the specific steps, it is important to note that they should be agreed and followed by both the technical partners in the project and the third parties selected, since without this collaboration the integration will not be possible. So, in order to assure this, the methodology will be firstly presented and confirmed among the Covid-X partners before the third-parties' on boarding and then it will be explained to them supporting a common understanding about the entire process.

Next sections will present each of the defined steps.

1.1 Information gathering

This initial phase consists of getting a deeper knowledge about the third-party proposal and solution to be integrated as the main inputs for the requirements definition, which is the next step.

For doing so, two main methods can be used:

1. Exhaustive checking of the proposal: this helps us to obtain general information from the document submitted to the call. Table 1 shows the main elements extracted from the proposal.

- Initial form to be filled in by the third party: this helps us not only to confirm the data obtained before, but also ask additional information or useful clarifications that will help their onboarding process. Table 2 shows the different details to be asked to the third party.

TABLE 1. INFORMATION TO BE EXTRACTED FROM THE PROPOSAL

Item	Description
SME name	Name of the organization
Proposal title	Title of the proposal
Proposal type	Single/Team solution
Additional partner	Additional partner in team solutions
Challenge	Challenge the proposal is addressing
Clinical partner	COVID-X Clinical partner to work with
Additional data	If additional data to be included in the sandbox

TABLE 2. INFORMATION TO BE ASKED THROUGH AN INITIAL FORM

Item	Description
Data from clinical partner	Specific variables or data to be accessed from the clinical partners
Open datasources	Open data sources to be accessed
Own data	Data to be uploaded to the sandbox
Own software	Software to be uploaded to the sandbox
Users and roles	Users to access the platform and associated roles
Logs access	If they want to have access to the logs
Add_data	Additional data to be included in the sandbox
Data visualization	If there is a need of providing visualizations of the data (through Kibana)
Additional info	Additional needs for the integration

1.2 Integration requirements definition

This step translates the information obtained in the previous one into the different requirements for the integration phase. By doing this, we will retrieve info about:

- The different users to access the system and their roles (permissions)
- The data to be accessible from the database for each third party (including the clinical partner's and the open data)
- The data to upload to the platform: format, size, metadata, etc.
- Software to include in the platform (dockerized).

5. The need of providing access to the log system.
6. Type of data visualizations.
7. Additional requirements according to the solution to be integrated

1.3 Integration process

After defining the different requirements, technical partners are able to start providing the different elements that guarantee the integration process and the third parties are allowed to use them to start interacting with the platform.

1.4 Issues solving

This step is in combination with the previous one, since the integration process is continuously monitored to detect specific issues or additional needs that may appear. For doing so, a continuous communication channel between third parties and technical partners is created according to their preferences. Once the integration is completed and every single issue is solved, we can go to the last step.

1.5 Final validation and follow up

This last phase assures the correct integration of the third-party solution into the platform. This is done in a two-level process: on one hand, with the confirmation by the third party (they should answer a validation form –to be defined-) and, on the other, by the technical checking within the platform. Moreover, this phase also covers the rest of the project's lifetime, since it oversees detecting and solving any specific issue that may occur afterwards.

2 General integration planning

This section presents the general schedule defined for the integration process as initially planned. The different durations for each step have considered not only the data gathering process that may be needed, but also the complexity of implementing and providing the different elements for allowing the integration. Figure 2 shows this planning, where day 0 is the starting day for the projects of the first open call:

FIGURE 2. INTEGRATION PLANNING STEPS

Although this is the initial planning, different modifications and delays may appear due to different reasons. The main risks for these deviations are presented in the following table, considering only the onboarding phase:

TABLE 3. RISKS THAT MAY AFFECT THE GENERAL INTEGRATION PLAN

Risk	Affected phase	Responsible	Plan
The initial form is not filled in on time	Information gathering	Third party	MContinuous follow up of the third parties' contributions and contact them if anything is missing
The initial form does not include some vital information	Information gathering	Technical partners	Detect the lack of this information and define a new way for obtaining it (additional form, direct communication, etc.)

Risk	Affected phase	Responsible	Plan
The information provided in the initial form is not clear	Requirements definition	Third party	Analyse the form responses and directly contact those partners that need to clarify different aspects
The requirements cannot be achieved (out of scope)	Requirements definition	Third party	Work on a common understanding of the technical capabilities to redefine the requirements
Lack of access to the third party's servers for deploying local instances of the platform	Integration process	Third party	Work with those who do not provide the access. Detect if there are technical, administrative or other kind of issues affecting this provision.

3 Integration process during 1st open call

3.1 Initial technical requirements provision

During the first open call we followed the methodology defined in Section 1. Nevertheless, with the aim of facilitating the process, the technical team defined a set of technical requirements to be considered and deeply analysed by the third parties even before sending their proposal.

TABLE 4. TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS PROVIDED FOR THE 1ST OPEN CALL

Id	Name	Description	Priority
1	Data Description/Management	Input data to be stored in the Covid-X sandbox and consumed by eHealth tools must follow the COVID-X Unified Semantic Data Model. The data model will follow and partially or fully implement some of the most widely accepted standards in the field of Health (HL7, FHIR, DICOM, ICD11, DCAT, etc.).	Mandatory
2	Early Data Availability	Initial data samples must be provided by Clinical partners and third parties, which may contain synthetic information but in the exact format/structure the real data will have. This will allow initial design and implementation of data ingestion tools to interact with the actual data sets.	Mandatory
3	Local Sandbox Deployment at Clinical partners Infrastructure	Data providers (clinical partners) must provide a local infrastructure to host a local deployment of the Covid-X sandbox. This will tackle the closed anonymized data access/distribution issues and will ensure GDPR and national regulations compliance.	Mandatory
4	Sandbox Integration, Testing and Deployment	Tools and services provided by third party SMEs must follow the integration, testing and deployment process with the Covid-X sandbox, the CI/CD and DevSecOps approach adopted by Covid-X sandbox.	Mandatory
5	Sandbox Components and third-party services integration	Covid-X sandbox components, including third party services and tools, must be provided in a containerised form (dockerized) with the appropriate configuration files and according to the underlying infrastructure, for their integration, testing and deployment at the Clinical Partners infrastructure.	Mandatory
6	Sandbox Cloud Deployment	The Sandbox will be deployed in a flexible Cloud infrastructure to accommodate the needs of the project.	Important

Id	Name	Description	Priority
7	On-Premise infrastructure of Clinical Partners	For the on-premises deployment of the Sandbox, for Clinical partners joining the program, container orchestration should be available. A Kubernetes infrastructure should be provided where the components will be deployed. If this is not available from the Clinical partners, hosts should be provisioned to deploy the Sandbox.	Important
8	On-Premise Host Specs for Clinical Partners	Typically for an initial local deployment at the Clinical partner infrastructure, a multi-core machine with 64GB of RAM should be available with SSD Drive(s). The disk space has to be a multiple of the data volume to be stored. Multiple hosts are an ideal setup of 3x64GB RAM or 3x32GB RAM, or 3x16GB RAM machines are significantly better and allow for a Highly Available setup.	Mandatory
9	Additional Resources at local infrastructure for Clinical Partners	Additional hosts should/could be added depending on needs.	Important
10	Local Infrastructure needs for GPUs	To accommodate the needs for model training in the Federated learning approaches investigated during the later stages of the project, the necessary GPU requirements should be clarified and anticipated in due time, leading ultimately to their provisioning from the respective Clinical Partners.	
11	Hosts Isolation at local infrastructure for Clinical Partners	The host(s) provided for the purposes of the project within each Clinical partners' premises should ideally be isolated from the remaining infrastructure for security purposes. Regular backups should be planned if possible.	Mandatory
12	Remote Access at local infrastructure for Clinical Partners	Clinical partners must allow remote access (SSH) to the machines to setup the necessary tools (Sandbox). Administrator privileges will also be required.	Mandatory
13	Secure Communications to/from Covid-X sandbox & Covid-X sandbox Security	The components exposing services to external systems or external systems integrated with the Covid-X sandbox should only allow encrypted communications and data transfer, using encryption protocols. Web and Dashboard components must only allow authenticated access over HTTPS.	Mandatory

Id	Name	Description	Priority
14	On-Premises deployment of third-party services & tools	Third party services have to be deployed on the clinical partners' locally deployed sandbox at their infrastructure enabling access and use of their anonymized data (in compliance to GDPR and national regulations).	Mandatory
15	Data Ingestion - Formats	The data (anonymized for closed data sets of Clinical partners) to be ingested in the Covid-X sandbox need to be of acceptable formats such as csv, json, xml, html, txt, etc. or through secure APIs following an acceptable JSON schema.	Mandatory
16	Data Ingestion	The data (anonymized for closed data sets of Clinical partners) that Covid-X sandbox will use must be available and reachable from the hosts provisioned. The data could reside or be loaded on the machine disk(s) or otherwise be easily reachable from the machine.	Mandatory
17	Data Indexing	The data loaded within the Sandbox will be indexed, made available and searchable enabling efficient retrieval and subsequent usage.	Mandatory
18	Third party services interfaces	Third parties' services have to provide their own APIs - as OPEN APIs specifications - to be connected to the platform (JSON or yaml).	Mandatory
19	Third party data integration & data anonymization	Third parties' data to be uploaded to Covid-X sandbox must be anonymized beforehand, meeting the GDPR requirements, handling the sensitivity of medical data properly, and ensuring the ingestion of only minimized and adequately anonymized data into the Covid-X sandbox. The recommended anonymization techniques include Generalization, Suppression, Noise injection and Permutation/Shuffling. The most common criteria to evaluate protection against re-identification are k-anonymity and l-diversity. To select the appropriate technique, a trade-off between risk of data being exposed and data utility is needed.	Mandatory
20	Third party services interaction	The third-party services implemented and interacting with the Elastic Stack should aim at providing specific access and functionality, over an encrypted role-based access fashion, providing thus a usage-specific functionality to external users	Mandatory

As above mentioned, this list was given during the open call timeframe. Once the different proposals were selected to participate in the project, the integration process previously defined really started.

3.2 Information gathering

3.2.1 Initial form

The initial form provided to the users was defined by the technical team of the Covid-X project. A set of 19 different questions were identified to gather information for the requirements definition:

TABLE 5. INITIAL QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE THIRD PARTIES

Id	Question
1	Which are the specific variables you want to access from the specific clinical partners of your selection?
2	Are you going to use any of the open data sources provided in the platform? Which one?
3	Are you planning to upload any kind of data to the platform?
4	Are you planning to integrate any kind of software into the platform?
5	Is this software dockerized?
6	How many users will need access to the platform?
7	Have all these users have the same role in the platform or do you need different ones (with different permissions)?
8	Do you plan to use Kibana for clinical data visualization?
9	Do your API calls / requests follow a common REST architecture? If not, describe the architecture used for the API calls.
10	What communication protocols do your API calls support (e.g. HTTP)?
11	Have you identified any vulnerabilities related to your organisation's infrastructure? If yes, please describe how you address them.
12	Regarding the threat landscape around your product, is there any imminent threat (e.g. software version vulnerabilities, end-of-support for your tools)?
13	Which of the Covid-X Sandbox security services (e.g. role-based access control, authentication and authorization) would you like to know more about during the training process?
14	Please inform us if there is any additional topic regarding the cybersecurity concerns of your organisation that you would like to have explained and discussed during the training process.
15	How much will your services interact with COVID-X sandbox (e.g. numbers of requests/API calls per hour/day etc.)?
16	Will there be any automated scheduled API calls to COVID-X sandbox?
17	Do your services require access to COVID-X via streaming cues?
18	Do you have any frustrations / concerns regarding the interaction of your services with COVID-X sandbox?
19	Do you plan to utilize the CI/CD services for the integration / testing / deployment of your service? If yes, please specify the services you are interested in (i.e. Jenkins Server, Docker Registry, SCM)

3.2.2 Second form

After this first phase focused on gathering initial information, a second stage was needed to clarify some aspects before starting the integration process. Each third-party solution was asked to provide some additional details regarding four main topics: data integration, software integration, cloud/local deployment for team solutions and finally GDPR compliance, personal and sensitive data protection. Appendix 2 includes this new information collector.

3.2.3 One to one meetings

Once all the previous information was gathered, a one to one meeting was planned with each third party to stipulate some final details. Next table shows the results of these meetings.

TABLE 6. MAIN INFORMATION GATHERING FROM ONE TO ONE MEETINGS

Third party	Covid-X Tech Partner	Meeting Date	Type of platform	Software integration	Comments
Aviate	8Bells	14/06/21 10:00	Centralized	No solution (hw)	
Vadi	8Bells	14/06/21 15:00	Centralized	Yes, applications dockerized	
LOMT	8Bells	14/06/21 13:00	ICH premises	Yes, applications dockerized	
KCoVRI	UPM	14/06/21 12:45	Local	No	Already provided a VPN access to their server with SSH
C@H	UPM	14/06/21 11:00	Centralized	No	
CAPTAIN-X	UPM	14/06/21 10:00	Centralized	No	
COVID@HOME	UPM	14/06/21 10:45	Centralized	No	
COV-ART	UPM	14/06/21 14:00	Local	Yes, applications not dockerized yet	Already provided a VPN access to their server
GASTON SCHOLAR	UPM	30/06/21 16:00	Centralized	Yes, applications not dockerized yet	
CARE4COVID	UPM	14/06/21 15:00	Centralized	Yes, applications dockerized	

Third party	Covid-X Tech Partner	Meeting Date	Type of platform	Software integration	Comments
TRAJECT	INTRA	14/06/21 10:00	Centralized	Yes, applications dockerized	
SEGTNAN	INTRA	14/06/21 12:15	Centralized	Yes, applications not dockerized yet	
ARM	INTRA	14/06/21 10:45	Centralized	No	
DDRhab	INTRA	14/06/21 13:00	Centralized	Yes, applications not dockerized yet	
MADCAP	INTRA	14/06/21 14:00	Centralized	No	
TRIAGE	INTRA	14/06/21 14:45	Centralized	No	

3.3 Integration documentation

Some specific documentation has been prepared and distributed to describe the integration process along three main aspects:

1. Security: the security consideration given to the users was focused on five main aspects for the sandbox: GDPR compliance, authentication process to access the platform, authorization according to the RBAC approach followed in the sandbox, encryption of the communication with and within the platform and finally a set of additional aspects to be considered. Appendix C includes the guide shared with the third parties.
2. API provision: this document includes the information about the endpoints to access different functionalities of the platform, mainly data accessing and provision and data visualization (Kibana). Appendix D includes the guide shared with the third parties
3. Software integration: this document includes a detailed user guide for the CI/CD platform. Appendix E includes the guide shared with the third parties.

3.4 Integration description

3.4.1 RBAC provision

The first steps towards integrating 3rd parties with the Covid-X Sandbox are the creation of spaces where each 3rd party will query, visualize and update its own data, as well as the creation of users for

each 3rd party organization, enabling them to perform the above actions to their data with reference to their role and respecting privileges.

Handling sensitive data raises the need for strong security measures to ensure compliance with GDPR and other applying national and European regulations. To that end, the Covid-X Team has configured a Role-Based Control Access (RBAC) System to guarantee a strong authentication and authorization mechanism for ELK Stack.

This mechanism determines who is realizing a certain request and whether they are allowed to execute it. The internal ELK native realm enables us to manage and authorize users. The Kibana interface, along with the elastic API provide ways to add and remove users, manage their passwords and assign them specific roles that entail specific sets of privileges.

The steps followed to set up the RBAC system for the Covid-X Sandbox are the following:

- 1 Index pattern creation: First, we created index patterns for each 3rd party whose data were to be ingested in the Sandbox. Additionally, we created two more index patterns: one to act as a data catalogue and another to accommodate the open-source data from the selected public sources.
- 2 Kibana space creation: Then, we created spaces that enable us to meaningfully categorize and structure the offered dashboards. We created one space per 3rd party organization to isolate data coming from different 3rd parties. Once inside a space, one can only see the dashboards belonging to that space. Furthermore, we control the features visible in each space. Of course, Kibana spaces are not meant to provide security; they are intended to provide more intuitive and well-structured visualizations. To ensure security, we created roles granting users the desired Kibana privileges that, in turn, assign users access to subsets of spaces or features.
- 3 Role creation: Next, we created roles for each group of users and assigned them different index and Kibana privileges. More specifically, we created two kinds of roles; one administrative role, with read and write privileges to the respective 3rd party indices; and one read-only role for the respective 3rd party indices. It is important to notice that no user from a certain 3rd party organization has privileges to read and/or write data from another 3rd party organizations, except for the System Owner. Moreover, apart from the privileges on the respective organization's indices, all roles have read-only privileges in the data catalogue and opensource indices, as well as the `viewed_index_metadata` privilege to all indices.
- 4 Security privileges: All previously created roles are assigned with some of the below privileges.
 - 4.1 Index privileges:
 - 4.1.1 `read`: Read-only access to actions.
 - 4.1.2 `write`: Privilege to perform all write operations to documents, including permission to index, update, and delete documents, perform bulk operations, and dynamic mapping updates.
 - 4.1.3 `view_index_metadata`: Read-only access to index and data stream metadata. This privilege is available for use primarily by Kibana users ¹.

¹ <https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/security-privileges.html>

- 4.2 Kibana privileges: Kibana privileges grant users access to features within Kibana. Roles have privileges to determine whether users have written or read access within a specific Kibana space.
 - 4.2.1 all: Grants full read-write access.
 - 4.2.2 read: Grants read-only access.
- 5 User creation: At last, we created users for each 3rd party organization. This was done in coordination with the 3rd parties; users' names and emails, as well as the desired roles for each user were provided to us by the 3rd parties. We used this input to create the users and assign them the appropriate roles, granting them the necessary privileges to only be able to do exactly what they are entitled to.

3.4.2 Data integration

Database population has taken place in the scheduled time frame with minor issues. The way it was checked consisted of a manual inspection in each deployment, both in local and central cases.

As it has already been aforementioned, API documentation was produced with detailed examples to show the different use cases that may occur involving data. Each SME had a specific way of interacting with the sandbox, and so, different endpoints needed to be used. The final aim of this stage was not only to assess the integration with the sandbox, but also to support the teams that had any problem when ingesting or retrieving data.

The process of developing the specific structure of each SME happened in an incremental manner. All core functionalities, RBAC and API provision were delivered to them as the development progressed, both not to overload the sandbox, and grant access as early as possible. Hence, the integration of data in each of the cases also progressed incrementally when new releases occurred, as each of the teams was able to access the sandbox.

In terms of the specific topic of data ingestion, we requested information from each SME (see appendix B) to access data specifications in terms of a data schema and a data sample. This data sample didn't need to be real, but had to follow the same spec as the real data that the sandbox would handle. This was the first step enabling us to create the data structure in elastic, data pipeline in Logstash and API endpoints in Kong. All these stages are described in the following subsections.

ELASTIC MAPPINGS

Elastic data types are referred to mappings in elastic terminology and define the structure of each document inserted into the index (table in elastic terminology) to which the mapping targets. They also act as filters of improperly formatted data as they reject all the documents that don't fit the schema perfectly.

Elastic mappings may not be defined when the use case allows data schema modification on the fly, or when there are several schemas that may coincide in the same index. In these situations, the mapping is created when the first document is ingested and is set up to dynamic. Moreover, when appropriate, elastic allows the definition of fixed structures that may include dynamic objects internally. In other words, the dynamicity can be set at any level in the hierarchy.

The initial approach of the team was to establish as strict (non dynamic) as many objects as possible since the unified data model and the federated functionality need to emanate from both static data schemas and fixed key names.

In order to accomplish such a complex task, all individual data samples were studied and converted to mappings triggered before the data ingestion. Thus, all the indices were created prior to the delivery of new releases with more SMEs involved.

There was a total of 48 data mappings integrated into the central deployment distributed among the SMEs, where each of those covers a specific index.

Name	Last commit	Last update
--		
aviate	Aviate pipeline and mappings completed.	3 months ago
care4covid	- new indices added for care4covid	1 month ago
carm	Added C_Arm pipelines and mappings	2 months ago
cath	Updated branch with main	2 months ago
covid@home	covidathome pipelines	2 months ago
ddrehab	DDRehab Features Dataset Setup	3 months ago
gaston	Fixed data mapping	3 months ago
karolinska	Changed name of <org> from captainx to karolinska	2 months ago
madcap	MadCap Dataset Pipeline	3 months ago
opensource	Update the novel-covid ingestion data	4 months ago
sermas	Added C_Arm pipelines and mappings	2 months ago
traject	Finalize traject mappings & pipelines	3 months ago
triage	Triage Dataset Pipeline Setup	3 months ago
vadi	fixed data mapping for vadi	1 month ago
data_catalogue.json	Update data_catalogue mappings	3 months ago

FIGURE 3. GITLAB VIEW OF THE FOLDERS COMPRISING THE DATA MAPPINGS OF THE CENTRAL DEPLOYMENTS OF THE SANDBOX.

LOGSTASH PIPELINES

The second stage, after establishing the structure of the indices, is to encapsulate the ingestion over a logstash pipeline, which is the unique entity capable of transferring clinical data into the elastic cluster. Logstash has several ways of being triggered, and in this specific case, it uses three different working modes: url poller (omitted as it has no interaction with SMEs), port listener and directory listener.

Each third party was requested their preferred type of ingestion, directory or port listener, giving as result the various use cases defined for each of the SMEs. More specifically, there were teams requesting only one mode, but there were a few requiring both functionalities.

Logstash pipelines were defined according to the structure of either file or request’s body, leading to use mainly two different plugins, csv and json, which handled the initial transformations and parsing. If necessary, data types were also transformed in some specific cases that could be of interest, such as fields containing dates.

There was a total of 31 different pipelines integrated into the central deployment distributed among the SMEs. Normally, the port listener had a mapping 1:1 with a pipeline config file, whereas the file listener was defined through a unique config file for all the different cases, depending on the path to which the API services uploaded the information.

Name	Last commit	Last update
..		
care4covid	- new indices added for care4covid	2 weeks ago
cath	Fix Load balancer endpoint for Vadi & cath pipelines	2 months ago
covid@home	Last f** check	2 months ago
vadi_pipelines	Fix Load balancer endpoint for Vadi & cath pipelines	2 months ago
aviate_pipeline.conf	Merge Vadi into master	2 months ago
carm_pipeline.conf	Added C_Arm pipelines and mappings	2 months ago
ddrehab_pipeline_audio.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
ddrehab_pipeline_csv.conf	Remove sinceb_path from all pipelines	2 months ago
ddrehab_pipeline_features.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
gaston_pipeline.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
http_pipeline.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
http_poller_pipeline.conf	Fix	2 weeks ago
karolinska_pipeline.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
madcap_pipeline_dynamic.conf	Remove document_id from http pipelines	2 months ago
madcap_pipeline_static.conf	Last f** check	2 months ago
open.covid-chestxrays.conf	Remove sinceb_path from all pipelines	2 months ago
open.novel-covid.conf	Remove sinceb_path from all pipelines	2 months ago
open.owid-covid.conf	Remove sinceb_path from all pipelines	2 months ago
sermas_pipeline.conf	Create Sermas Data Mappings	2 months ago
traject_pipeline.conf	Remove sinceb_path from all pipelines	2 months ago
trriage_pipeline.conf	Remove document_id from http pipelines	2 months ago

FIGURE 4. GITLAB VIEW OF THE DIRECTORY CONTAINING THE LOGSTASH PIPELINES FOR THE CENTRAL DEPLOYMENT OF THE SANDBOX

API PROVISION

The last stage prior to the delivery of the new SME specific functionalities was to create the endpoints capable of triggering Logstash for data ingestion and interacting with elastic (except for the data ingestion) and Kibana.

In order to define all different endpoints needed, and as the information that Kong needs in declarative mode is redundant, a python script was developed to automatically create this config file in every release. The data structure containing all the information related to third parties in the central deployment is shown below.

```
INDEX_SEARCH = {
  'opensource': ['owid-covid*', 'covid-chestxrays', 'novel-covid*'],
  'aviate': ['sensors'],
  'traject': ['records'],
  'sermas': ['patient'], # used by segtnan team
  'ddrehab': ['5sst', '6mwt', '6mwt_r', '9hpt', 'accelerometer',
              'arat', 'audio_transcription',
              'barthel', 'bb', 'breathing', 'gyroscope', 'hst',
              'hunova', 'mrc', 'neuroeval',
              'parameters', 'pgwbi', 'sppb', 'tmt', 'tug',
              'features'],
  'triage': ['conversations'],
  'gaston': ['laboratory'],
  'care4covid': ['dailysummary', 'device', 'patient', 'question',
                 'gemellilongitudinal', 'gemelliprofiles'],
  'madcap': ['static', 'dynamic'],
  'ki': ['userdescription'],
  'covidathome': ['oxygen', 'questionnaire'],
  'vadi': ['audiometadata', 'clinicalmetadata',
           'questionnairemetadata'],
  'cath': ['patient_data', 'patient_data_covid', 'patient_readings',
           'patient_readings_covid'],
  'carm': ['patient']
}

STREAM_WRITES = {
  'aviate': {
    'sensors': '8083'
  },
  'ddrehab': {
    'audio_transcription': '8081',
    'features': '8089'
  },
  'triage': {
    'conversations': '8082'
  },
  'gaston': {
    'laboratory': '8084'
  },
  'care4covid': {
    'dailysummary': '8085',
    'device': '8086',
    'patient': '8087',
    'question': '8088',
    'gemellilongitudinal': '8103',
    'gemelliprofiles': '8104'
  },
  'madcap': {
    'static': '8091',
    'dynamic': '8092'
  },
  'ki': {
    'userdescription': '8090'
  },
  'covidathome': {
    'oxygen': '8093',
    'questionnaire': '8094'
  },
  'vadi': {
    'audiometadata': '8099',
```

```
'clinicalmetadata': '8100',
'questionnairemetadata': '8101'
},
'cath': {
'patient_data': '8095',
'patient_data_covid': '8096',
'patient_readings': '8097',
'patient_readings_covid': '8098'
},
'carm': {
'patient': '8102'
}
}
FILE_WRITES = {
'opensource': ['owid-covid', 'covid-chestxrays', 'novel-covid'],
'traject': INDEX_SEARCH['traject'],
'sermas': INDEX_SEARCH['sermas'],
'ddrehab': ['5sst', '6mwt', '6mwt_r', '9hpt', 'accelerometer',
'arat', 'barthel', 'bb', 'breathing', 'gyroscope',
'hst', 'hunova', 'mrc', 'neuroeval',
'parameters', 'pgwbi', 'sppb', 'tmt', 'tug']
}
```

Where each of the first level data structures stores, respectively, all the indices in the sandbox per SME, including open source data; the Logstash pipelines triggered through a http request with the defined port; and the indices populated through a file write in disk memory.

As the integration of more SMEs succeeded, new information was added to these data structures and Kong was restarted to deliver the new changes. It is also important to note that the API works closely to the RBAC functions of elastic, as every ingestion request must be authorized by the flask service.

There were over 200 different endpoints integrated into the central deployment, with some common for all users such as Kibana and the scroll endpoint, and the vast majority covered the use cases of specific third parties. Appendix D covers all the information delivered to the third parties.

3.4.3 Local deployments

There were several cases requiring a local solution hosted by the clinical partners of the SMEs. The list of local deployments comprises LOMT, KCoVRI and COV-ART, where LOMT is a single solution hosted in the GCP belonging to ICH.

In general, all three cases were deployed by following the next steps:

1. Create the sandbox core functionalities, i.e. ELK stack, and add the data mappings to the respective indices.
2. Deploy the API services, flask service and Kong, with just the endpoints for the targeted SME.
3. Create roles, users and spaces in Kibana so that users can access the desired functionalities.

LOMT/ICH

This deployment was hosted in GCP so the unique requirement needed to be fulfilled consisted of linking a google account to their virtual machine. After that step, we had full access to the host with sudo privileges. The deployment targeted just one VM.

KCoVRI

Their clinical partner provided a VPN access enabled by using the public key of one person of the technical team. OpenVPN was used to connect to their premises, and ssh to connect to each of their three machines. The deployment covered the three machines, hence elastic worked as a cluster and the load balancer targeted all the three elastic nodes.

COV-ART

The clinical partner of this solution is a public University; thus, they have a custom VPN server and there was an unavoidable issue when trying to connect the local host to the central based Jenkins and Jfrog services.

Hence, not only the three generic steps were executed, but also the deployment of Jenkins and Jfrog. Jenkins was configured to use the host as a worker, therefore avoiding using the docker container for that purpose. In both cases, roles were created so the user could access the desired functionalities.

3.4.4 Software integration

Several third-party teams utilized the COVID-X Sandbox CI/CD Stack to automatically build, test, deploy, and integrate their software solution into the Sandbox platform. The teams that could not benefit from the automated software integration process, due to some hardware limitations (e.g., hardware-based applications, software application strictly bound to the team’s own infrastructure, etc.), proceeded with manual integration testing of their applications with the Sandbox core services.

The integrated software solutions were Dockerized applications comprised of one or multiple Docker containers. In some cases, the teams uploaded their application source code to the project’s private Version Control System (VCS) repositories, i.e., Gitlab. These teams could utilize the full CI/CD pipeline features for development, unit testing, integration testing, and deployment tasks. On the other hand, some organizations did not commit their source code in the project’s Gitlab repositories and decided to upload a pre-built Docker image to the Sandbox private Docker registry. These Docker images were employed by Jenkins pipelines that deployed the application, ran some functional and integration tests with the Sandbox management services, and, if successful, deployed the applications to the Sandbox operational environment. Table 7 summarizes the teams that achieved software integration with the sandbox core services, and the tools of the CI/CD they used.

TABLE 7. TEAMS THAT ACHIEVED SOFTWARE INTEGRATION WITH THE SANDBOX CORE SERVICES

Third-Party	Source Code in Gitlab	Docker Image in Docker Registry	Jenkins Pipelines	Sandbox Operational Environment
TRAJECT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LOMT	No	Yes	Yes	Yes (Sandbox local deployment at ICH Premises)
KCoVRI	No	Yes	Yes	Yes (Sandbox local deployment at KCoVRI Premises)

Third-Party	Source Code in Gitlab	Docker Image in Docker Registry	Jenkins Pipelines	Sandbox Operational Environment
Care4covid	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
COV-ART	No	Yes	Yes	Yes (Sandbox local deployment at COV-ART Premises)

RBAC methods and practices were followed for providing access to the CI/CD tools and applications, as described in the following sections.

3.4.4.1 Version Control System (Gitlab)

Gitlab is the selected tool to host the source code repositories of the core Sandbox services and the third-party software tools. The first step was to create a dedicated private Gitlab group to host the source code repositories. More sub-groups are made under the main group to organize the repositories of the third-party teams, as depicted in Figure 5. Only specific users from the respective team have read and write permissions to the repositories for which they are responsible.

FIGURE 5. OC1 SOURCE CODE REPOSITORIES IN GITLAB

3.4.4.2 JFrog Docker registry

JFrog is a private Docker registry used for storing and managing the generated Docker images. A dedicated repository is created to support each software component/application utilizing the Sandbox CI/CD Stack. Users from the third-party teams are granted access only to the specific repositories created for their team. Docker images were either built, tagged, and stored in the Docker registry directly by a team member or were automatically built and pushed by the Jenkins server. Figure 6 presents a snapshot of the created JFrog repositories.

FIGURE 6. SANBOX REPOSITORIES FOR OC1

3.4.4.3 Jenkins CI/CD Server

Jenkins is the CI/CD server that supports the end-to-end CI/CD workflows for building, testing, deploying, and integrating software applications/components into the Sandbox platform. Dedicated workspaces have been created for all teams using the Sandbox CI/CD Stack, as depicted in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7. JENKINS WORKSPACES FOR OC1.

Users from each organization have been granted access only to specific Jenkins workspaces, within which they can create, modify, and run the Jenkins pipelines connected to the applications for which they are responsible. This is feasible when installing and using the “Role-Based Authorization Strategy”, shown in the following Figure 8.

FIGURE 8. SANDBOX ROLE-BASED AUTHORIZATION STRATEGY.

This Jenkins plugin allows creating permission roles that can be assigned to Jenkins users, limiting each user's read and write capabilities to the specific workspaces of their applications. Figure 9 presents the list of roles created for the third-party teams, and the associated permissions.

Item roles

Role	Pattern	Credentials					Job								
		Create	Delete	ManageDomains	Update	View	Build	Cancel	Configure	Create	Delete	Discover	Move	Read	Workspace
api-services	"api-.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
care4covid	"oc1/care4covid.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
covart	"oc1/covart.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
ddrehab	"oc1/ddrehab.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
gaston	"oc1/gaston.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
lomt	"oc1/lomt.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
mgmt-services	"mgmt-.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
security-services	"security-.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
segtnan	"oc1/segtnan.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
traject	"oc1/traject.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										
vadi	"oc1/vadi.*"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										

FIGURE 9. JENKINS ROLES

3.4.4.4 Sandbox Operational Environment

A dedicated virtual server has been reserved and provided to each third-party team to integrate their software application into the Sandbox. Each server is configured to run a secured Docker Daemon, also accessible over the network to allow remote and automated deployment of Dockerized applications, either through the Jenkins CI/CD pipelines or through any other testing and integration system. Furthermore, a Portainer service is installed on each server to ease the Docker resources management and monitoring for the team's developers and administrators. Effective firewall rules are configured on each virtual server to securely handle inbound and outbound network traffic, ensuring that only authorized users and applications are permitted to attain access.

3.5 Issue solving

Supporting tasks covered all the interaction steps of SMEs with the sandbox. Specifically, we provided technical support covering Docker, Jenkins, API and Kibana. This section covers both technical assistance for the teams and SMEs additional requests in this order.

Assistance to the teams comprised all the interactions needed to clarify any doubts they could have related to the sandbox. The following events sum up these interactions:

TABLE 8. SET OF ONE-TO-ONE MEETINGS FOR SUPPORT

Third party	Covid-X Tech Partner	Meeting Date	Topic	Channel
Care4Covid, C@H	UPM	02/06/21	Docker support	Meeting
DDRehab	UPM	10/06/21	Docker support	Meeting
COV-ART	UPM	24-30/07/21	Docker support	Slack
Care4Covid	UPM	27/07/21	Docker, CI/CD support	Meeting
ALL	8Bells	01-30/07/21	RBAC configuration	Slack

The second topic of this section refers to the implementation of the SMEs requests and summarizes the constantly updated requirements the Covid-X sandbox had to meet to properly integrate their data and software. The most common issues that we came across during this process were updating data mappings and creating new indices.

Several SMEs asked for updates in terms of ingestion pipelines, which triggered a procedure with the following stages:

1. Collect the new data sample from the SMEs.
2. Recreate the data mappings and Logstash pipelines in an ELK test deployment.
3. Check that the new sample is correctly ingested into Elastic.
4. Delete the old structured index from production (if it existed).
5. Create the index with the newly introduced fixes.

Moreover, some of the API functions were explicitly requested by the end users, specifically delete and scroll endpoints. The first refers to the deletion of data from an index, but not the actual index; meanwhile the second enables pagination (see D2.3 for further information). Both were implemented in the API and delivered to the SMEs in both central and local deployments.

Furthermore, we were in constant communication with the SMEs through the corresponding communication channels in Slack, to identify the number of users that should access data in their organization, along with the respective roles and privileges. The configuration of the RBAC system is tailor-made for each 3rd party organization and aims to ensure maximum security and GDPR compliance through appropriate user Authentication and Authorization, based on the principle of minimum privileges.

3.5.1 Technical questions in Slack

Once the sandbox was prepared, a new communication channel was enabled through Slack to help with the technical integration. The following table presents some of the questions made by the SMEs together with their responses:

TABLE 9. SOME OF THE TECHNICAL QUESTIONS MADE THROUGH SLACK CHANNEL

Third party	Date	Question	Response
VADI	12/04/21	<p>Can we access the platform?</p> <p>What would be the advantage of using the sandbox?</p> <p>Storage & computational power are free in the sandbox?</p> <p>We use Google cloud platform for storage and computational power; do we have to replace it or keep both?</p> <p>Is a sandbox or deployment?</p> <p>How long will the sandbox last?</p> <p>How much data can we store?</p> <p>How are you managing issues?</p> <p>Will data we store be private or shared data?</p> <p>Is there any voice data from COVID19 patients available on the sandbox we could get access to?</p> <p>Can we use sandbox also for other clients?</p>	<p>Through the FAQ document (appendix A)</p>
DDRehab	07/05/21	<p>What is the action plan for access/training on the sandbox?</p>	<p>Planning for the webinars</p>
TRAJECT	07/05/21	<p>Information about the security in the sandbox</p>	<p>Through the sandbox security document (appendix C).</p> <p>Having the clinical data in the sandbox is technically possible, but only possible if the clinical partner agrees (if they allow their data to leave their servers).</p> <p>With regards to the type of data to be stored, the sandbox is not designed to store multimedia data initially</p>
TRAJECT	01/06/21	<p>Do you know in which Hetzner datacenter you will have the sandbox instance?</p> <p>Do you know if it performs data encryption at rest?</p>	<p>All the sandbox virtual servers are located in Nuremberg, Germany and they support encrypted storage at rest</p>
CAPTAIN-X	16/06/21	<p>Will you share the Jenkins template file?</p>	<p>We will share the template repositories</p>

Third party	Date	Question	Response
KCOVRI	08/07/21	Do you have a target timeline to deliver the sandbox container for teams utilising a local instance of the sandbox?	Since you envision a local deployment, we will first need to access your local infrastructure to deploy the sandbox locally. We will approach you ASAP to get the information needed
CAPTAIN-X	09/07/21	Do you plan to post an openapi collection for the API?	By now we have no plans of doing this
VADI	17/07/21	Got a 403 [Forbidden] when trying to call with my credentials	There is an issue with the /catalogue index and you cannot reach it at the moment. We are working on fixing this issue. In the meanwhile, you can check the table with the available indices and API endpoints in the API documentation.
Care4Covid	19/07/21	Have you provided credentials for accessing Jenkins and/or JFrog?	Credentials for the DI/CD environment will be provided tomorrow after somebody from the technical team contacts you to gather the needed info.
DDRehab	23/07/21	DDrehab API seem not to work when sending files with same name and different content	Normally you should be able to ingest multiple files with the same name, so we assume there is an issue with this process. We will optimize the Logstash services to handle this better
Care4Covid	26/07/21	We are receiving a 502 from nginx when trying to reach JFrog	Thanks for notifying this, JFrog is now back online

Third party	Date	Question	Response
MADCAP	27/07/21	We are having an issue with one of the ingest_stream endpoints	There was a small issue on the ingestion pipeline for this index, but it should be working as expected now.
LOMT	12/08/21	JFORG returns 502 Bad gateway error	Fixed
TRAJECT	10/09/21	We are having problems with Jenkins. It seems like a bug	We have upgraded Jenkins to the latest version (v2.311) as well as the installed plugins
Care4Covid	5/10/21	Could you please provide a Google drive url for the API specification?	Surely, done.

4 Conclusions

According to the information given, the integration process has been done and finalised during the first Sprint of the OC1 for all the SMEs participating in the programme as expected. As explained in this document, this has been a complex process and requiring allocation of considerable efforts to accomplish the objective of having the different solutions working with the sandbox. In this regard, the definition of a specific methodology, the information gathering for having all the requirements before starting the process, the integration process itself and finally the issue solving step have been performed during these months for this purpose.

Appendix A: FAQ- the COVID-X Sandbox (April 2021)

Here you can find a list of the most common questions about the sandbox:

1. When are we going to be able to use the sandbox?

First version of the sandbox will be released by the end of April. We will make a general announcement as soon as we have it ready.

2. What kind of functionalities will the sandbox provide?

Main functionalities to be provided are related to access, visualization and ingestion of clinical data. We will also provide different tools to allow the deployment of software solutions within the platform to run your own models, following a CI/CD approach. These software solutions should be dockerized.

3. How can we use the sandbox?

It depends on your specific solution. The sandbox is a common tool and a mandatory requirement for the deployed containers to access clinical data, so you have to decide how this can help you in providing your solution.

4. Who can use the sandbox?

The sandbox will be available for the team and single solution partners. It will be deployed on the clinical premises in case the 3rd party healthcare providers do not give their consent to move their anonymized data to the cloud-based deployment. These partners should assure the availability and the minimum computational capabilities needed to do so.

5. What kind of data will be available in the sandbox?

Each instance of the sandbox includes clinical data from the related clinical partner. It also includes some open data previously selected according to their relation to the different challenges. It store any other data the partners decide to ingest, following a specific structure (the one already in the platform or a new one provided by the team). The data model will be ready together with the platform.

6. Are we able to store data in the sandbox?

Yes, you are. A specific API allows you to ingest data into the sandbox, and the harmonization and management module include them in the ElasticSearch structure.

7. Will the stored data be private or public?

We follow a role-based access control, so your data will be accessible only to the members of your choice.

8. Storage and computational power are free in the sandbox?

Multimedia data are not going to be ingested in the platform, just the metadata and url. Other types of data can be annotated and stored if allowed.

9. How are the issues in the server going to be managed?

The system is designed with fault tolerance in mind. Moreover, there will be a support team helping with the deployment of the sandbox. Nevertheless, since this is not a commercial project, we cannot support 24/7, just only during working days.

10. How long will the sandbox last?

As long as the project lasts. It can last longer if the platform finally goes commercial.

11. How much time do we have to make the integration with the sandbox?

This integration should be finished by the end of the first sprint, i.e. the third month of your project (July 2021).

12. Are you going to prepare any technical webinar to provide more details?

Yes, we are preparing three specific webinars:

- Data visualization using Kibana
- Dockerization for software ingestion.
- CI/CD services
- Dates will be previously announced.

13. How can you help us in the integration process?

We have identified three main steps:

- Information gathering: this initial phase helps us understand more about your solution and needs. We obtain the information from your proposal and from the initial form.
- Integration requirements definition: this phase translates the information obtained in the previous one into the different requirements for the integration.
- Integration process: this is the main phase, when the teams and single solutions make the integration according to the initial requirements.
- Issue solving: the integration process is continuously monitored to detect any specific issues and try to solve them as soon as possible.

As you know, the technical contact point is Silvia Uribe (UPM): sum@gatv.ssr.upm.es.

Appendix B: COVID-X Technical Information Collection from Third Parties

1. Data Integration

The COVID-X Sandbox, 1st release, provides the proper endpoints to ingest information coming from data providers both for historical data at clinical partners as well as real-time collected data. In short, the core COVID-X Sandbox services of closed and open data integration, real-time data ingestion, data annotation, indexing, cataloguing and storing, security, data access/filtering/search/querying and data visualization, along with an API Gateway compose this release, as shown in the following figure.

To successfully implement data integration, it is thus important that you provide us with more details on the following aspects related to ingested data:

- What kind of data will be ingested in the COVID-X Sandbox?
- Does your solution involve hardware components? If yes, how will the data be transmitted to the Sandbox; what protocols will be used?

- Which is the format of the ingested data (e.g. csv files, json files, etc.)? Please reply separately for real-time collected data and for historical data sets.
- How will this data be accessible by the COVID-X Sandbox (e.g. REST APIs, FTP server, etc.)? Please reply separately for real-time collected data and for historical data sets.
- Which is the description schema of the datasets (dataset variables, types of values, value ranges if applicable) that will be ingested in the COVID-X Sandbox? Data providers must provide synthetic/sample data that follow the same data schema.
- Is there an estimation on the size/volume of the data to be ingested in the COVID-X Sandbox?
- How often does COVID-X Sandbox need to poll datasets access points for updated or newly inserted data (e.g. daily/weekly/monthly or at a specific time)? How many different types of hardware devices/sources will be streaming data into the platform? How many devices of each type will send their data? What is the collection/sampling frequency rate of each type?
- Does your solution envision use of open data sources? If yes, which exactly? Will they need to be ingested in the COVID-X Sandbox?

2. Software Integration

COVID-X to support software integration, testing and deployment activities, provides a CI/CD stack and relevant tools (Gitlab code repository, Jenkins, Docker registry, etc.). These are to be used by solution providers to integrate their solutions with the COVID-X Sandbox services, test and deploy the integrated system to the selected deployment infrastructure.

The development workflow in the CI/CD environment is as follows:

For efficient access and technical support to solution providers, we would like the following information from your side:

- Will you commit the source code of your software solution to the COVID-X Gitlab code repository – private project per third party solution?

- If not, is your software solution dockerized? If not, it will need to be dockerized (after complete unit testing) and the docker container to be uploaded to the COVID-X private docker registry for integration and testing with the COVID-X Sandbox services.
- What are the minimum resource requirements for your software solution (CPU, Memory, Disk storage)?
- Does your software need any kind of hardware accelerator (GPU, TPU, ...). If so, have in mind that the cloud deployment does not provide any accelerator.
- Do you plan to have any kind of internal communication between your docker containers? If so, which protocol will you be using? What kind of data is involved?
- Are there any additional constraints for the software integration of your solution with the COVID-X Sandbox that we need to know?
- Please provide a list of the individuals (name and email address) that will be granted access to the CI/CD environment.
- Please, provide a list of the individuals (Gitlab username, email) that will be granted access to the Gitlab.

3. Cloud / Local Deployment - Team solutions

An operational version of the COVID-X Sandbox (**centralized instance**) is deployed on cloud infrastructure provided by the COVID-X consortium – historical data to be ingested in this instance should be anonymized, if personal/sensitive, and real-time data collection/aggregation should follow all the processes required by GDPR.

For team solutions, to address the clinical partners' needs to maintain their historical sensitive/personal data sets at their own legally certified infrastructure, there is also the option to deploy the Sandbox, integrated with the software solution, locally at the infrastructure that the Clinical partner/Data Controller will provide (local instance). Even in this case, the ingested historical data sets should be anonymized, while for real-time collected data, again all the processes required for GDPR compliance should be followed.

To gather aggregate needs for deployment, we kindly ask you to provide us with the following information:

- According to the above descriptions/specific context of use in your solution, which instance of the COVID-X Sandbox will you use (centralized or local)?
- If you need a local instance, what kind of infrastructure (number of machines, CPU, Memory, Disk storage) you will dedicate to setup and use the COVID-X Sandbox? What kind of remote access can you provide to system integrators to execute administrative tasks and deployment processes?

- In the case of a local deployment, an HTTP secure certificate might be needed. It applies only to third parties that will deploy a sandbox in their instances. In case the third party does not provide it, then self-signed certificates could be generated.

4. GDPR compliance, Personal and sensitive data protection

As mentioned in 3), any historical personal/sensitive data to be ingested in the Sandbox need to be anonymized (following the provisioned anonymization guidelines), while any real-time collected data must follow all processes for GDPR compliance. It is absolutely necessary to follow these processes. To understand the actual context per solution with respect to personal/sensitive data and how they will be handled, and ensure GDPR is enforced, we would like you to respect and follow all the required guidelines to be GDPR-compliant. It is necessary to answer the following points, to verify that every aspect of COVID-X Sandbox will not violate at any point GDPR guidelines:

- Do you collect in real-time/from any devices/apps personal/sensitive data according to GDPR? What processes do you follow to comply with GDPR in that respect?
- If you further provide historical data sets (clinical partners), including personal/sensitive data, what anonymization processes/methods have you used/will you use to anonymize them before ingesting them into the Sandbox?

Appendix C: Sandbox security document

TABLE 7. SECURITY DETAILS ACCORDING 5 MAIN ASPECTS: GDPR, AUTHENTICATION, AUTHORIZATION, ENCRYPTION AND OTHER SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS

Aspects	Information
GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only anonymized data is accepted in the Sandbox. To that end, users may use the Anonymization Guideline provided by the consortium in the framework of D1.1. → Users should also consult D1.1 Ethical and Legal Framework for more information. - Users have the right to retain / delete their data from the Covid-X Sandbox at any moment. - Users have the right to update their data at any moment. - Data is only and constantly available to those that own them and to the system owner. - Data is stored in the Covid-X Sandbox only for the purposes of the project as agreed between the 3rd parties and the Covid-X Consortium and only for the lifetime of the project. - Users should be notified in case an incident threatening their data takes place.
Authentication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users are created by the admin (username, password). - Users are encouraged to change their password when they first login to Covid-X Sandbox services. - Users have two ways of accessing the Sandbox: through Kibana GUI or through the Kong Gateway. - Users are encouraged to use sufficiently complex passwords. - Users are encouraged to frequently change their passwords and not share them with anyone in any way.
Authorization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When users are created by the administrators, roles are assigned to them (RBAC). - The administrators relate each role with specific permissions. - Users can only access the indices necessary to perform the analysis specified in their proposal, as submitted in OC#1 of the COVID-X project.
Encryption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When users connect to Kibana, end-to-end encryption is enabled to protect users' credentials and data transferred. - When users connect to Kong, end-to-end encryption is enabled to protect users' credentials and data transferred. - Internal Sandbox communication is encrypted to protect data transfer.

Aspects	Information
Other security considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- 3rd party healthcare providers are encouraged to keep backups of their data.- Users should not integrate within the Covid-X Sandbox any illegitimate software.- Users should be aware of suspicious messaging and browsing to compromise the privacy of their account and data in any way (COVID-X partners will in no case ask you to provide your password).

Appendix D: Sandbox API SPEC

Summary of the reachable endpoints

The following table illustrates all the reachable endpoints exposed with kong.

Method	Endpoint	Description
POST	/api/ingest_stream/<org>/<index>	targets logstash service ingesting in a specific index
POST	/api/ingest_file/<org>/<index>	upload a file into the logstash target folder. File upload must be a multipart request with "file" key
GET/POST	/api/search_index/catalogue	returns data catalogue information stored in elastic
GET/POST	/api/search_index/<org>/<index>	elastic DSL query targeting specific index
GET/POST	/api/scroll	query with pagination
GET (browser)	/	kibana GUI exposed on the root path
-	/client/search_index	endpoint for PL clients

Further details with examples

Note: words placed inside comparison symbols (< >) indicate the user needs to replace it with the proper content. **To have a general idea of indices and teams please refer to the catalogue endpoint.**

Reminder: every request must have its auth as shown in the examples

- Kibana

On the browser just specify the url of the sandbox without any appended path. For example, in the case of the cloud environment:

<https://sandbox.covidx.rid-intrasoft.eu/>

- Endpoints

/api/search_index/catalogue: there is a special index in the sandbox that contains information related to the indices used by all the teams. All the users from all the teams are able to call this endpoint to retrieve the name of their own index. It can include a body containing typical DSL syntax.

Example commands:

```
curl --request GET 'https://sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/catalogue \  
--header 'Authorization: Basic <base64 AUTH>'
```

/api/search_index/<org>/<index>: it provides the typical elastic functionalities to search a specific index. The query must have the [DSL](#) syntax and it can include a body. The examples below show how you can place the credentials in the query with curl.

Example commands:

```
curl --request GET 'https://sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/<org>/<index> \\  
--header 'Authorization: Basic <base64 AUTH>' -d '  
{  
  "query" : {  
    "match_all" : {}  
  }  
'
```

```
curl --request GET 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/<org>/<index>
```

```
curl --request POST 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/<org>/<index>'
```

```
curl --user <username>:<password> --request POST  
'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/<org>/<index>
```

/api/ingest_stream/<org>/<index>: each organization requiring stream-like ingestion capabilities is provided with their own endpoints to target their index. This request must have the body established in the data schemas requested. **This endpoint should be used if you are directly passing information with an application/json format directly in the body of the request.**

Example commands:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/ingest_stream/<org>/<index> --header 'Content-Type:  
application/json' --data-raw '{"foo": "bar"}'
```

/api/ingest_file/<org>/<index>: all organizations requiring batch-like ingestion capabilities are provided with a specific endpoint responsible for triggering the “sandbox-ingestfile” container. This container saves the file included in the request. The following example assumes the existence of the target file called “file1.csv”. **This endpoint should be used if the information is stored inside a file and you want to update it to be ingested automatically. The file must have the key “file” for the process to succeed, as shown in the example.**

Example commands:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/ingest_file/<org>/<index>' --form  
'file=@"/home/user/desktop/file1.csv"'
```

/api/delete_on_index/<org>/<index>: allows delete operations in a specific index with [DSL](#) syntax. As the search API, it supports json body format specifying the query that selects the documents to be deleted.

Example commands:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/delete_on_index/<org>/<index>' --header 'Content-Type:  
application/json' --data-raw '{"query": {"match_all": {}}}'
```

/api/delete_on_team/<org>: allows delete operations in all indices an organization can access. It uses the same structure as the previous endpoint. **USE WITH CAUTION.**

Example commands:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://<username>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/delete_on_team/<org>' --header 'Content-Type: application/json' --  
data-raw '{"query": {"match_all": {}}}'
```

- *Programming language clients*

Set host to **/client/search_index**. SSL must be enabled. It only supports sea

Example commands:

```
es = Elasticsearch(hosts='https://<usr>:<password>@sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu:443/client/search_index', ssl=True)
```

```
res = es.search(index="<org>.<index>", body={"query": {"match_all": {}}})
```

- *Query with pagination*

To request a huge amount of documents, the [scroll](#) operation is enabled through a two-step iterative call. As the elastic documentation describes, first a scroll argument is passed to the normal search_index endpoint, and then subsequent calls are done targeting the scroll endpoint, as shown below.

FIRST CALL

/api/search_index/<org>/<index>?scroll=<duration>: creates the connection and keeps it alive for <duration> time units.

SECOND CALL

/api/scroll: subsequent calls with the token received in the response of the first call should target this endpoint.

Example commands:

FIRST CALL

```
curl -XPOST -u <username>:<password> 'https://sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/search_index/<org>/<index>?scroll=1m -H "Content-type:  
application/json" --data \  
{  
  "size": 10,  
  "query": {  
    "match_all": {}  
  }  
}
```

SUCCESSIVE CALLS

```
curl -XPOST -u <username>:<password> 'https://sandbox.covidx.rid-  
intrasoft.eu/api/scroll' -H "Content-type: application/json" --data \  
,  
{  
  "scroll" : "lm",  
  "scroll_id" : "<scroll_id>"  
}
```

Sandbox Indices and APIs

Organization	Dataset	Ingest Data API	Ingest data type	Retrieve Data API	Notes
opensource	OWID Covid19 (Github)	-	-	/api/search_index/opensource/owid-covid	
	covid-chestxray-dataset	-	-	/api/search_index/opensource/covid-chestxrays	
	Novel Coronavirus	-	-	/api/search_index/opensource/novel-covid	
aviate	Sensors	/api/ingest_stream/aviate/sensors	JSON Data	/api/search_index/aviate/sensors	
traject	Records	/api/ingest_file/traject/records	JSON Files	/api/search_index/traject/records	
segtnan / SERMAS	patient	/api/ingest_file/sermas/patient	CSV Files	/api/search_index/sermas/patient	
ddrehab	5sst	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/5sst	CSV Files	/api/search_index/ddrehab/5sst	
	6mwt	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/6mwt		/api/search_index/ddrehab/6mwt	
	6mwt_r	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/6mwt_r		/api/search_index/ddrehab/6mwt_r	
	9hpt	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/9hpt		/api/search_index/ddrehab/9hpt	
	accelerometer	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/accelerometer		/api/search_index/ddrehab/accelerometer	
	arat	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/arat		/api/search_index/ddrehab/arat	
	audio_transcription	/api/ingest_stream/ddrehab/audio_transcription	JSON Data	/api/search_index/ddrehab/audio_transcription	
	barthel	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/barthel		/api/search_index/ddrehab/barthel	

Organization	Dataset	Ingest Data API	Ingest data type	Retrieve Data API	Notes
	bb	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/bb	CSV Files	/api/search_index/ddrehab/bb	
	breathing	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/breathing		/api/search_index/ddrehab/breathing	
	gyroscope	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/gyroscope		/api/search_index/ddrehab/gyroscope	
	hst	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/hst		/api/search_index/ddrehab/hst	
	hunova	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/hunova		/api/search_index/ddrehab/hunova	
	mrc	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/mrc		/api/search_index/ddrehab/mrc	
	neuroeval	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/neuroeval		/api/search_index/ddrehab/neuroeval	
	parameters	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/parameters		/api/search_index/ddrehab/parameters	
	pgwbi	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/pgwbi		/api/search_index/ddrehab/pgwbi	
	sppb	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/sppb		/api/search_index/ddrehab/sppb	
	tmt	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/tmt		/api/search_index/ddrehab/tmt	
	tug	/api/ingest_file/ddrehab/tug		/api/search_index/ddrehab/tug	
		features		/api/ingest_stream/ddrehab/features	JSON Data
covid19trriage	conversations	/api/ingest_stream/triage/conversations	JSON Data	/api/search_index/triage/conversations	
lomt / ICH	ammissioni_ps	/api/ingest_file/ich/ammissioni_ps	CSV Files	/api/search_index/ich/ammissioni_ps	Available in the Sandbox local
	degenze	/api/ingest_file/ich/degenze		/api/search_index/ich/degenze	
	diagnosi_ps	/api/ingest_file/ich/diagnosi_ps		/api/search_index/ich/diagnosi_ps	

Organization	Dataset	Ingest Data API	Ingest data type	Retrieve Data API	Notes
	d_motivo_ricovero	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_motivo_ricovero		/api/search_index/ich/d_motivo_ricovero	deployment at the ICH premises
	d_prestazioni	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_prestazioni		/api/search_index/ich/d_prestazioni	
	d_terapie	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_terapie		/api/search_index/ich/d_terapie	
	lab	/api/ingest_file/ich/lab		/api/search_index/ich/lab	
	parametri_vitali	/api/ingest_file/ich/parametri_vitali		/api/search_index/ich/parametri_vitali	
	prestazioni	/api/ingest_file/ich/prestazioni		/api/search_index/ich/prestazioni	
	terapie	/api/ingest_file/ich/terapie		/api/search_index/ich/terapie	
	trasferimenti	/api/ingest_file/ich/trasferimenti		/api/search_index/ich/trasferimenti	
	comorb	/api/ingest_file/ich/comorb		/api/search_index/ich/comorb	
	diagnosi	/api/ingest_file/ich/diagnosi		/api/search_index/ich/diagnosi	
	d_lab	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_lab		/api/search_index/ich/d_lab	
	d_parametri_vitali	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_parametri_vitali		/api/search_index/ich/d_parametri_vitali	
	d_provenienza	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_provenienza		/api/search_index/ich/d_provenienza	
	d_tipo_ricovero	/api/ingest_file/ich/d_tipo_ricovero		/api/search_index/ich/d_tipo_ricovero	
	microbiologia	/api/ingest_file/ich/microbiologia		/api/search_index/ich/microbiologia	
	pazienti	/api/ingest_file/ich/pazienti		/api/search_index/ich/pazienti	
	spostamenti	/api/ingest_file/ich/spostamenti		/api/search_index/ich/spostamenti	
terapie_ps	/api/ingest_file/ich/terapie_ps	/api/search_index/ich/terapie_ps			

Organization	Dataset	Ingest Data API	Ingest data type	Retrieve Data API	Notes
	ventilazione	/api/ingest_file/ich/ventilazione		/api/search_index/ich/ventilazione	
	curated_pcr_db	/api/ingest_file/ich/curated_pcr_db		/api/search_index/ich/curated_pcr_db	
kcovri	entries	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/entries	CSV Files	/api/search_index/kcovri/entries	Available in the Sandbox local deployment at the kcovri premises
	feeling	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/feeling		/api/search_index/kcovri/feeling	
	measurements	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/measurements		/api/search_index/kcovri/measurements	
	medication	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/medication		/api/search_index/kcovri/medication	
	note	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/note		/api/search_index/kcovri/note	
	symptom	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/symptom		/api/search_index/kcovri/symptom	
	triggers	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/triggers		/api/search_index/kcovri/triggers	
	vitals	/api/ingest_file/kcovri/vitals		/api/search_index/kcovri/vitals	
care4covid	dailysummary	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/dailysummary	JSON Data	/api/search_index/care4covid/dailysummary	
	device	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/devices		/api/search_index/care4covid/device	
	patient	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/patient		/api/search_index/care4covid/patient	
	question	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/question		/api/search_index/care4covid/question	
	gemellilongitudinal	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/gemellilongitudinal		/api/search_index/care4covid/gemellilongitudinal	
	gemelliprofiles	/api/ingest_stream/care4covid/gemelliprofiles		/api/search_index/care4covid/gemelliprofiles	
gaston scholar	laboratory	/api/ingest_stream/gaston/laboratory	JSON Data	/api/search_index/gaston/laboratory	
madcap	static	/api/ingest_stream/madcap/static		/api/search_index/madcap/static	

Organization	Dataset	Ingest Data API	Ingest data type	Retrieve Data API	Notes
	dynamic	/api/ingest_stream/madcap/dynamic	JSON Data	/api/search_index/madcap/dynamic	
captainx / ki	userdescription	/api/ingest_stream/ki/userdescription	JSON Data	/api/search_index/ki/userdescription	
covart	measures	/api/ingest_file/covart/measures	CSV Files	/api/search_index/covart/measures	Available in the Sandbox local deployment at the cov_art premises
covid@home	oxygen	/api/ingest_stream/covidathome/oxygen	JSON Data	/api/search_index/covidathome/oxygen	
	questionnaire	/api/ingest_stream/covidathome/questionnaire		/api/search_index/covidathome/questionnaire	
c@h	patient_data	/api/ingest_stream/cath/patient_data	JSON Data	/api/search_index/cath/patient_data	
	patient_data_covid	/api/ingest_stream/cath/patient_data_covid		/api/search_index/cath/patient_data_covid	
	patient_readings	/api/ingest_stream/cath/patient_readings		/api/search_index/cath/patient_readings	
	patient_readings_covid	/api/ingest_stream/cath/patient_readings_covid		/api/search_index/cath/patient_readings_covid	
vadi	audiometadata	/api/ingest_stream/vadi/audiometadata	JSON Data	/api/search_index/vadi/audiometadata	
	clinicalmetadata	/api/ingest_stream/vadi/clinicalmetadata		/api/search_index/vadi/clinicalmetadata	
	questionnairemetadata	/api/ingest_stream/vadi/questionnairemetadata		/api/search_index/vadi/questionnairemetadata	
carm	patient	/api/ingest_stream/carm/patient	JSON Data	/api/search_index/carm/patient	

Appendix E: User guide for the CI/CD platform

COVID-X Programme

Sandbox Software Integration Guide

Introduction

This document provides guidance to the COVID-X Sandbox CI/CD Stack that supports the deployment, testing, and integration of Dockerized software components. This document is intended to be used by the development teams of the third-party solutions onboarded during the first COVID-X Open Call.

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1. Software Dockerization

Summary of the steps:

- Create an application with a design based on microservices
- Decide which base image is better for your specific case
- Create a Dockerfile
- Create a docker-compose.yml file that contains all the services (optional)
- Run your application either with docker run or with docker-compose up

Step 1: Create an application

The most common use case of the Sandbox is related to data-driven solutions. Data-driven solutions usually involve algorithms that work and extract useful information from data and expect inputs and outputs. Hence, there are two ways to proceed:

- Run your algorithms as a client of other services (e.g., Elasticsearch).
- Run your algorithms as a server by using the Flask framework.

The first case involves requesting data to somewhere else by using some DB connector. These connectors are supported for several languages and can straightforwardly make requests. For example, in Python, there is a library that offers these functionalities called Python Elasticsearch Client¹. This way, a docker container could host a TensorFlow instance running training jobs. By using this approach, there is no need to have access to the data, as only the algorithm can do so.

The second case usually occurs when the algorithm is already trained, so it is required to expose this service, acting as part of the backend of a GUI (or a shell tool). This way, the TensorFlow instance waits for instances to come and processes them either on the fly or in batches, depending on the desired behavior. The Flask framework offers the necessary REST API communications by exposing the defined port².

As a reminder, in the case of having access to the host, there is also the possibility of creating trained models, logs, or any other type of file from within the container and sharing it with the host by binding a folder.

¹ <https://elasticsearch-py.readthedocs.io/en/v7.13.3/>

² <https://theaisummer.com/deploy-flask-tensorflow/>

Step 2: Choose the base image

Dockerhub offers multiple pre-built images that can be used to run any type of model. The most common cases might be Tensorflow or Pytorch deep learning algorithms, but there exist much more pre-built images that can save hours of work. For instance, let's suppose that a developer wants to create a Tensorflow service like the ones mentioned above. First, the image must be chosen, and there are several options:

- Using Tensorflow-GPU image
- Using Python image and install Tensorflow-GPU in the Dockerfile
- Using an entire OS such as CentOS and installing both Python and Tensorflow in the Dockerfile

As you may know, Python offers seamless interoperability with other programming languages. This is the actual case of Tensorflow, which is written in C++, or Pytorch, written in Lua. When selecting a base image, one should always have in mind that the requirements of such complex frameworks can make the build process time demanding.

To sum up, choose the image closer to what you would expect from a ready environment and avoid building tools in the Dockerfile.

- Tensorflow image: <https://hub.docker.com/u/tensorflow/>
- Pytorch image: <https://hub.docker.com/r/pytorch/pytorch>

Step 3: Create a Dockerfile

Once the application has been implemented, now it is the turn of its Dockerization. During the Docker webinar, we talked about the ins and outs of the Dockerfile³. For example, to run a Flask instance, the Dockerfile may be as follows:

```
FROM alpine
WORKDIR /usr/src/app
COPY . .
RUN apt add --no-cache python3 py3-pip
RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
CMD ["python3", "app.py", "--host", "0.0.0.0", "--port", "80"]
```

³ https://github.com/BorjaArroyo/docker_webinar

As another example, to run a Tensorflow instance, the Dockerfile could be as follows:

```
FROM tensorflow
WORKDIR /usr/src/app
COPY . .
CMD ["python3", "app.py"]
```

Step 4: Create a docker-compose.yml file

The docker-compose file makes the process of running containers straightforward. Instead of placing all the options inside the command line docker run sentence, those can be defined in a much more verbose YAML configuration file.

This is an example of docker-compose.yml file:

```
version: '2.2'
services:
  es01:
    image: elasticsearch:7.13.2
    container_name: elasticsearch
    environment:
      - cluster.name=docker-cluster
      - bootstrap.memory_lock=true
      - "ES_JAVA_OPTS=-Xms512m -Xmx512m"
      - xpack.security.enabled=false
      - discovery.type=single-node
    ulimits:
      memlock:
        soft: -1
        hard: -1
    volumes:
      - data01:/usr/share/elasticsearch/data
    ports:
      - 9200-9200
    networks:
      - elastic
  logstash:
    image: logstash:7.13.2
    container_name: logstash
    environment:
      ELASTIC_USERNAME: elastic
```



```
ELASTIC_PASSWORD: elastic
ELASTICSEARCH_HOST_PORT: http://elasticsearch:9200
ports:
  - 8081:8081
networks:
  - elastic
volumes:
  - ./pipeline:/usr/share/logstash/pipeline

volumes:
  data01:
    driver: local

networks:
  elastic:
    driver: bridge
```

The file can be split into three core parts:

- **Services:** all the containers that must run are placed here. The image is either built with the build option or pulled from a Docker registry. Note that when an image with that tag exists, docker-compose does not rebuild it automatically.
- **Volumes:** allow the containers to read and write into folders located at the standard host directory system.
- **Networks:** allow the services to communicate among them without publishing ports into the host system.

In the previous example, all the images are pulled from Dockerhub and none of them is built, but in the next one, the Dockerfile directory is specified in the yaml file:

```
version: '3.7'

networks:
  net:
    name: net
    external: true

services:
  loadbal-tester:
    build:
      context: ../
      dockerfile: ./dockerfiles/Dockerfile_loadbal
    image: loadbal-tester
    container_name: loadbal-tester
```



```
networks:
  - net
restart: on-failure
environment:
  - "USER=user1"
  - "PASSWORD=pw1"
```

So each time a docker-compose build is ordered, it creates the Dockerfile_loadbal image by placing it where the context specifies.

During the Docker webinar, we also explained the functionalities offered in this file in detail, so I encourage the reader to visit the GitHub repo⁴.

Step 5: Run the dockerized application

This step is usually the easiest one after all the previous tasks are done. There are two options, and the best practices are the following:

- Use docker run if only one service needs to be created, and its configuration can be introduced easily in the terminal.
- Use docker-compose up whenever the process starts being overwhelming in the terminal.

For example, in order to run the last docker-compose config file and supposing that its name is docker-compose_file1.yml, the order should be:

```
docker-compose -f docker-compose_file1.yml up -d
```

If there were several services, the desired ones could be specified after the -d option:

```
docker-compose -f docker-compose_file1.yml up -d loadbal-tester
```

In the case of an app with no docker-compose.yml file, the following two commands build and create/execute the container:

```
docker build -t covidx/app1:2.0 .
```

```
docker run --name app1 covidx/app1:2.0
```

⁴ https://github.com/BorjaArroyo/docker_webinar

2. Sandbox CI/CD Stack

2.1 Architecture

The Sandbox CI/CD stack comprises several open-source software tools, which collectively aim to create an automated build system capable of integrating changes performed by developers working on different services of the Sandbox. In addition to that, the Sandbox CI/CD stack acts as a testing and system integration environment for effectively testing, integrating, and deploying the software services of the Sandbox in a stable operational environment.

FIGURE 1: SANDBOX CI/CD STACK

The software components that synthesize the Sandbox CI/CD platform are the following:

- **GitLab⁵**: An easy yet powerful and intuitive git Version Control System (VCS). It offers a web-based graphical interface with several built-in features, such as version control, issue tracking, code review, wiki, etc. Multiple developers can concurrently create, merge and delete parts of the code they are working on independently at their local system before applying the changes to the shared GitLab repository.
- **Jenkins⁶**: An open-source automation server that acts as the CI/CD server, responsible for automating the parts of software development related to building, testing, and deployment of applications. Some of the tasks that can be automated through Jenkins include software builds, unit testing, packaging, and pushing of container images to the Docker Registry.
- **Docker Daemon⁷**: Services running on multiple development virtual servers for the deployment of containerized services. Docker Daemon is a background process that manages Docker images, containers, networks, and storage volumes. The Docker Daemon constantly listens to Docker API requests and processes them.
- **JFrog Docker Registry⁸**: A server-side application that stores and lets you distribute Docker images. It is used to securely control where the container images are being stored and how they are distributed.
- **Portainer⁹**: An open-source tool for managing container-based applications in various virtualization environments. It can be used to set up and manage the environment, deploy applications, monitor application performance, triage problems, and enable role-based access control.

2.2 CI/CD Workflows

Figure 2 depicts an example CI/CD workflow. In this scenario, developers (from their premises) can commit source code changes, implementing new component features or integration endpoints, and push their code to GitLab, the central source code repository in this environment. This event automatically triggers Jenkins to pull, compile, build and test the latest version of the source code from the specific feature branch of the code repository. If the unit tests finish successfully, Jenkins will use Docker to create a Docker image, which will then be pushed to the private JFrog Docker Registry with an appropriate tag. Finally, once components have been built and their images have been pushed to the Docker Registry, they are available to be pulled from any server with access to the said registry. This final step can be included in the Jenkins pipeline to deploy the newest version of the application to a predefined development environment, allowing further system integration and User Acceptance (UA) tests to be executed.

⁵ <https://gitlab.com/>

⁶ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

⁷ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁸ <https://jfrog.com/>

⁹ <https://www.portainer.io/>

FIGURE 2: CI/CD WORKFLOW

2.3 Source Code vs Docker Images

Development teams can choose one of the following two options:

- Commit the source code of their applications to a private Gitlab repository. Jenkins will use the source code for building the application, running any defined source code unit tests, building and storing the Docker images into the private Docker registry, running any defined integrations tests, and finally deploying a stable version of the application in the Sandbox operational environment.
- Push a pre-built Docker image of their application into the private Docker registry. In this scenario, Jenkins will pull the latest image from the private Docker registry, run the defined integration tests, and deploy a stable version of the application in the Sandbox operational environment.

FIGURE 3: SOURCE CODE VS DOCKER IMAGES

2.4 Access to the CI/CD Stack

A dedicated account will be created for each member of the third-party development teams. These accounts will have access to specific workspaces created for each of the software components that will be integrated into the Sandbox operational environment.

2.4.1 Gitlab

Each partner who wants to push source code to the COVID-X code repository must have a Gitlab account. You can sign up in Gitlab using the following URL: https://gitlab.com/users/sign_up

Then a separate Gitlab project will be created for each partner under the [COVID-X project](#). Partner must provide their email accounts associated with Gitlab to be invited to the respective Gitlab repository.

Each Gitlab project should have:

- Jenkinsfile: Define the Jenkins Pipeline as code
- Dockerfile: File for building the Docker application
- docker-compose.yml (optional): Deploy Dockerized application

An example of a Gitlab project is provided in: <https://gitlab.com/covid-x-prj/test-projects>

2.4.2 Jenkins

A Jenkins account will be provided to each partner with write permissions on specific workspaces. After that, a username/password will be communicated to each partner to start creating pipelines.

The URL of the Jenkins server is the following:

<https://static.170.190.130.94.clients.your-server.de>

How to create and configure a Jenkins pipeline

1. Create a New Item in Jenkins.
 - o Enter an item name. It is recommended to give a name that matches the Gitlab project and the associated branch (/master or /development)
 - o Select Pipeline and click OK
2. In the General tab, please select Gitlab Connection: "Gitlab".
3. The Build Triggers define when the Pipeline runs. In the Build Triggers tab, select the following options:

4. Click on the "Advanced" option and generate a Secret Token. Keep the token as it will be used for connecting the Gitlab repository with the Pipeline.

5. Notice the GitLab webhook URL on the option title. Keep the URL as it will be used for connecting the Gitlab repository with the Pipeline.
6. There is the option to launch a job after another project is finished. In such a scenario, where the job needs to be launched after another job is finished (ex: integration test-jobs, acceptance test jobs, etc.), the following option needs to be checked, referencing the job that precedes:

7. In the Pipeline tab:
 - o Definition: Pipeline script from SCM
 - o Add the Repository URL (e.g. <https://gitlab.com/covid-x-prj/<my-software-module>.git>)
 - o Add your Gitlab credentials (username/password)
 - o In "Branches to build", add either branch (e.g. */master,*/development, etc.)

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Add Script Path (e.g., Jenkinsfile)

8. Save the configuration

How to create a Gitlab webhook to trigger the Pipeline:

- On the Gitlab repository that needs to be connected to the created Jenkins pipeline, navigate to Menu > Settings > Webhook page:

- Fill the URL and Secret Token fields with the ones produced in the Jenkins pipeline.
- Select the Gitlab events that you want to trigger a new build of the Pipeline.
- Select "Add the webhook" when you are done. A new project hook appears at the bottom of the page. You can run a test to check that the Pipeline is successfully launched.

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Project Hooks (1)

<https://static.53.190.202.116.clients.your-server.de/project/test-rest-project>
Test Edit Delete

Push Events Merge Requests Events SSL Verification disabled

Firewall settings for Jenkins

- It is essential to communicate your external IP address to allow your machine through the Jenkins server's firewall. Otherwise, the firewall will block the connection.
- The following IP address must be allowed by your network administrator to be able to access the machine with Jenkins:
Jenkins VM: 94.130.190.170 port: 443

2.4.3 JFrog Private Docker Registry

A private Docker Registry has been deployed, allowing users to push/pull Docker images. It uses encryption over SSL and user authentication. The URL of the Docker Registry is the following:

<https://static.133.181.202.116.clients.your-server.de>

It is highly recommended that partners push their docker images to the private docker registry before the deployment. The stored images can be pulled and deployed in either the development or the deployment environment.

An example of how users can utilize the Jenkins pipeline to push or pull images to and from the private Docker registry can be found in the Jenkinsfile of the example project.

<https://gitlab.com/covid-x-pri/test-projects>

In case needed, we will provide an account for accessing the GUI of the JFrog Container Registry. This GUI allows to:

- view the different versions of the docker images in a secure way
- view the history of the image
- delete tags that are not needed anymore

Firewall settings for Private Docker Registry

- ✓ It is essential to communicate your external IP address to allow your machine through the Registry server's firewall. Otherwise, the firewall will block the connection.
- ✓ The following IP address must be allowed by your network administrator to be able to access the machine with Docker Registry:

Docker Registry VM: 116.202.181.133 port: 443

